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BUSINESS VISION

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Vol. 5 No. 1 (Jan. - June) 2009

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“INDIAN CAPITAL MARKET – RECENT REFORMS AND INITIATIVES”

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“INDIAN CAPITAL MARKET – RECENT REFORMS AND INITIATIVES”

INTRODUCTION

The Indian Capital Market today presents a vastly different picture from what it was a decade ago with lot of checks and balances in place, ensuring transparency in dealing and protection of the interests of the investors. Capital market is one of the most segments of the Indian financial system. It is the market available to the companies for meeting their requirements of the long term funds. It refers to all the facilities and the institutional arrangements for borrowing and lending funds. In other words, we can say that capital market is concerned with the raising of money capital for purposes of making long term capital and claims on it. In the capital market, much investment is made directly and internally financed by existing business firms known as internal accruals. These funds are directly employed in the long term fixed assets without the help of financial institutions in raising these funds. Household sector also meets the long term funds requirement of borrowing firms directly through primary market and indirectly through financial institutions for term lending. Capital market can be divided into various segments such as primary and secondary market, equity or debt market, mortgaged market, stock market and securities market and so on.

The Indian capital market is broadly divided into the Gilt-Edged Market and the Industrial Securities Market.

1. **The Gilt-Edged Market:** It refers to the market for Government and semi-government securities, backed by the RBI. Government securities are tradeable debt instruments issued by the Government for meeting its financial requirements. The term gilt-edged means ‘of the best quality’, because the government securities do not suffer from risk of default and are highly liquid. The RBI performs its function of open market operations in such securities.
2. **The Industrial Securities Market:** It refers to the market which deals in equities and debentures of the corporates. It is further divided into primary market and secondary market.
 - **Primary Market:** It is also known as new issue market. It deals with new securities i.e. securities which were not previously available and are

offered to the investing public for the first time. It is the market for raising fresh capital in the form of shares and debentures. The new offerings by the companies are made either as an initial public offering or rights issue.

- **Secondary Market:** It is also known as old issues market or stock exchange. It is the market for buying and selling securities of the existing companies. Under this, securities are traded after being initially offered to the public in the primary market and /or listed on the stock exchange. The stock exchanges are the exclusive centres for trading of securities.

CAPITAL MARKET IN INDIA

The capital market has in recent days, thanks to investment bankers and financial intermediaries captured the imagination of the common investor as a vehicle for wealth creation. So much so that the activity in the capital market has become the barometer for economic health and optimism.

The primary market activity has for years remained as an economic growth indicator.

Macro-economic parameters such as Gross Domestic Production, Index of Industrial Production, Foreign Direct Investment, cross-border trade, movement in stock indices, etc., were in sync with the growth in public offers made by the corporate sector.

A significant change observed in the last couple of years is that the vocabulary of the capital market has entered the lexicon of common and retail investors. New issues on offer as well as daily market movements are discussed passionately, almost like discussions on cricket matches are. Reinforcing the interest is the remarkable rally in the stock market since 2002.

Coming to Indian context, the term capital market refers to only stock markets as per the common man's ideology, but the capital markets have a much broader sense. Where as in global scenario, it consists of various markets such as:

- Government securities market
- Municipal bond market
- Corporate debt market
- Stock market
- Depository receipts market
- Mortgage and asset-backed securities market
- Financial derivatives market
- Foreign exchange market

STRUCTURE OF INDIAN CAPITAL MARKET

In India, many of the above markets are not developed to the required extent, and some does not even exist.

A capital market can provide huge impetus to the development of any economy so, it can be said that the growth and sustainability of capital markets plays an important role towards the development of the economy.

It is being observed that huge fluctuations are happening in Indian capital market in recent past, but with the help of proper mechanism, which is being observed in India and after examining various risk factors involved in capital markets, we attempt to say that the growth which has been observed in Indian capital market in recent past is a reality, but not a myth.

In India the capital market consists of

- Stock market
- Bonds, convertible debentures and debt market

- New issue market and merchant banking

There are no special markets for the trading of municipal bonds, asset backed securities, foreign exchange market and depository receipts market.

Right from the independence, thanks to steps initiated by the Indian government especially after the post liberalization era. A huge growth has been observed in the aspects of quality and quantity. Huge increase has been observed in the volumes of trade.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

1. Several studies for instance, Sahni (1985), Kothari(1986), Raju (1988), Lal (1990), Chandra (1990), Raghunathan (1991), L. C. Gupta (1992) and Sinha (1993) comment upon the Indian Capital Market in general and trading systems in the stock exchanges in particular and suggest that the systems therein are rather antiquated and inefficient and suffer from major weakness and malpractices. According to most of these studies, significant reforms are required if the stock exchanges are to be geared up to the envisaged growth in the Indian capital market.
2. Pandya (1992) observes that as a regulatory and development body, SEBI's efforts in the direction of investor protection are varied and unlimited. The measures brought in by SEBI broadly cover measures for allocative efficiency in the primary market with fair degree of transparency, reforms in the secondary market for visible and mutual funds, regulation of various market intermediaries and above all for the protection of the investing public.
3. From an academic point of view, the most significant work in the field of new issues in India is that of Gujarathi (1981) who examined the question of the risk adjusted return in the new issues market. As in all studies of new issues, the difficulty of estimating the risk (beta) of newly issued securities forces Gujarathi to use a complicated methodology for arriving at the risk adjusted return. His conclusion is that investors in the new issues market in 1970's earned an extra normal return of nearly 2½ percent per month.
4. Venkateshwar (1991) explores the relationships of the Indian stock markets as reflected by the Bombay Stock Exchange Index, vis-a-vis other prominent

international stock markets. 23 international Stock indices are used over the period 1983-87. He concludes that there is practically no meaningful relationship between the BSE index and other international stock market indices, though the British and South Korean indices are inversely related to BSE.

5. In his book L. C. Gupta (1992) concludes that, a) Indian stock market is highly speculative; b) Indian investors are dissatisfied with the service provided to them by the brokers; c) margins levied by the stock exchanges are inadequate and d) liquidity in a large number of stocks in the Indian markets is very low.

CAPITAL MARKET TRENDS

The Capital Market trends are classified into two categories, namely;

(A) Primary market trends

(a) Bull Market

A bull market tends to be associated with increasing investor confidence, motivating investors to buy in anticipation of future capital gains. India's BSE Index Sensex was in a bull run for almost 1 year from Jan 2007 to Jan 2008 as it increased from 14000 points to 21000 points.

(b) Bear Market

A bear market is described as being accompanied by widespread pessimism. Investors anticipating further losses are motivated to sell, with negative sentiment feeding on itself in a vicious circle.

(B) Secondary market trends

A secondary trend is a temporary change in price within a primary trend. These usually last a few weeks to a few months. A temporary decrease during a bull market is called a correction; a temporary increase during a bear market is called a bear market rally.

Whether a change of direction is an intermediate correction or rally, or if it is the start of a new trend, can be determined only with hindsight. When trends begin to appear, market analysts debate whether it is a correction/rally or a new bull/bear market, but it is impossible to tell. A correction sometimes foreshadows a bear market. Efficient market theoreticians consider these as just names used for convenience to describe the accumulation of what they consider random market movements over a period of time.

(a) Correction

A market correction is sometimes defined as a drop of 10% to 20% over a short period of time. It differs from a bear market mostly in that it has a smaller magnitude and duration. Because of depressed prices and valuation, market corrections (if it were possible to identify them as such) could be a good opportunity for value-strategy investors. If one buys stocks when everyone else is selling, the prices will be low and therefore the P/E Ratio goes down. Thus one can purchase 'undervalued' stocks with upside potential.

(b) Bear market rally

A bear market rally is sometimes defined as an increase of 10% to 20%.

Bear market rallies are typically very sharp, sudden, and short-lived.

FACTORS AFFECTING THE GROWTH OF CAPITAL MARKET IN INDIA

Turnover and trading in the capital market has increased manifold than it was a one and a half decade back particularly before liberalisation in 1991. Following factors may be said to have contributed in this growth:

- 1. Setting up of SEBI:** Securities and Exchange Board of India was established in 1988 and given statutory recognition in 1992 which has created an environment for equity culture amongst investing people.
- 2. Increasing Awareness:** Increasing awareness towards various investment opportunities has excited people to watch and invest in rewarding capital market instruments. Business newspapers, financial publications have made the people more aware about new long-term investment in security market.
- 3. Growth of Mutual Funds:** UTI was the only mutual fund till 1987 when State Bank of India and Canara Bank established their mutual funds. Till 1993, there were 7 public sector mutual funds, which have now increased to more than 50 with more than 300 schemes in their fold.
- 4. Growing Confidence:** Post liberalisation witnessed increasing interest in stock markets. Traditional investor in bank fixed deposits and post office saving schemes have shown preference in favour of shares and debentures.

5. **Stock Exchange:** Number of stock exchanges has gone to 23. Of these National Stock Exchange set up in November 1992, marks a radical change from past operations.
6. **Financial Services:** Merchant Banking, Credit Cards, Funds Transfer, Technical Consultancy, Brokerage, Custodial Services, Leasing, Portfolio Management and more recently Depository Services have contributed a lot to capital market to let it grow.
7. **Crediting Rating Agencies:** Credit rating mechanism provides guidance to investors /creditors in deciding risk associated with a debt instrument which helped in healthy development of capital market. CRISIL, ICRA and CARE are operating in India.

GLOBALIZATION AND THE INDIAN CAPITAL MARKET

With the gradual opening up of the Indian economy, increasing importance of foreign portfolio investment in the Indian markets and drastic reduction in import tariffs that has exposed Indian companies to foreign competition, Indian capital market is acquiring a global image. Till recently, participants in the Indian capital market could largely afford to ignore what happened in other parts of the world. Share prices largely behaved as if the rest of the world just did not exist.

At present, in sharp contrast to recent past, Indian capital market responds to all types of external developments, like US bond yields, the value of the peso or for that matter of any other currency, the political situation in China, or new petrochemical capacity in South Korea, etc.

In short, the Indian capital market is on threshold of a new era. Gradual globalization of the market will mean four things, namely:

- The market will be more sensitive to developments that take place abroad.
- There will be a power shift as domestic institutions are forced to compete with the FIIs who control the floating stock and are in control of the GDR market.
- Structural issues will come to the fore with a plain message: reform or despair.
- The individual investor in his own interest will refrain from both primary and secondary market; he will be better off investing in mutual funds.

CAPITAL MARKET REFORMS

The Indian regulatory and supervisory framework of securities market in India has been adequately strengthened through the legislative and administrative measures in the recent past. The regulatory framework for securities market is consistent with the best international benchmarks, such as, standards prescribed by International Organisation of Securities Commissions (IOSCO). Recent capital market reforms and an agenda for reforms are given below:

1. Extensive Capital Market Reforms were undertaken during the 1990s encompassing legislative regulatory and institutional reforms. Statutory market regulator, which was created in 1992, was suitably empowered to regulate the collective investment schemes and plantation schemes through an amendment in 1999. Further, the organization strengthening of SEBI and suitable empowerment through compliance and enforcement powers including search and seizure powers were given through an amendment in SEBI Act in 2002. Although dematerialization started in 1997 after the legal foundations for electronic book keeping were provided and depositories created the regulator mandated gradually that trading in most of the stocks take place only in dematerialized form.
2. Till 2001 India was the only sophisticated market having account period settlement alongside the derivatives products. From middle of 2001 uniform rolling settlement and same settlement cycles were prescribed creating a true spot market.
3. After the legal framework for derivatives trading was provided by the amendment of SCRA in 1999 derivatives trading started in a gradual manner with stock index futures in June 2000. Later on options and single stock futures were introduced in 2000-2001 and now India's derivatives market turnover is more than the cash market and India is one of the largest single stock futures markets in the world.
4. India's risk management systems have always been very modern and effective. The VaR based margining system was introduced in mid 2001 and the risk management systems have withstood huge volatility experienced in May 2003

- and May 2004. This included real time exposure monitoring, disablement of broker terminals, VaR based margining etc.
5. India is one of the few countries to have started the screen based trading of government securities in January 2003.
 6. In June 2003 the interest rate futures contracts on the screen based trading platform were introduced.
 7. India is one of the few countries to have started the Straight Through Processing (STP), which will completely automate the process of order flow and clearing and settlement on the stock exchanges.
 8. RBI has introduced the Real Time Gross Settlement system (RTGS) in 2004 on experimental basis. RTGS will allow real delivery v/s. payment which is the international norm recognized by BIS and IOSCO.
 9. To improve the governance mechanism of stock exchanges by mandating demutualisation and corporatisation of stock exchanges and to protect the interest of investors in securities market the Securities Laws (Amendment) Ordinance was promulgated on October 12, 2004. The Ordinance has since been replaced by a Bill.

RECENT INITIATIVES IN INDIAN CAPITAL MARKET

The recent initiatives undertaken in the Indian Capital Market are mentioned herein below:

- 1) **Reforms in Government Securities Market:** The Government has initiated a number of steps to strengthen the capital market such as:
 - (a) Auction system for sale of gilt securities;
 - (b) Securities Trading Corporation of India was set up in June 1994 to develop an institutional structure of security market;
 - (c) System of primary dealers was introduced in 1995
 - (d) Market orientation to issue Government securities paved the way for RBI to activate the open market operations as a total of market interventions;
 - (e) Commercial banks and mutual funds allowed to invest increasingly in government securities;

(f) The interest income on Government securities was exempted from TDS.

2) Informal Group on Primary Market: SEBI considered on priority basis the recommendations made by the 'Informal Group on Primary Market' and accepted most of the recommendations, including the following, for immediate implementation:

(a) Primary issues to be compulsory made through the depository mode;

(b) 100 percent book building in respect of issues of Rs. 25 crore and above;

(c) Reduction in the minimum number of mandatory collection centres in respect of issues above Rs. 10 crore to four metropolitan cities plus the place having the regional stock exchange.

3) Corporation and Demutualization of Stock Exchanges: Out of the 23 erstwhile stock exchanges, 18 have since been corporatized and demutualised in 2007-08. One stock exchange, i.e. Hyderabad Stock Exchange, failed to demutualise by the due date and has therefore been de-recognized. Saurashtra Kutch Stock exchange, Mangalore Stock exchange and Magadh Stock exchange have been de-recognized for various irregularities/non compliances. As regards Coimbatore Stock Exchange which had sought voluntary withdrawal of recognition, the matter is sub-judice.

4) Corporate Bond Markets: The Government had set up a High-Level Expert Committee on Corporate Bonds and Securitisation (Patil Committee) to look in to legal, regulatory, tax and market design issues in the development of the corporate bond market. The Committee submitted its report to the Government in December, 2005. The Budget of 2006-07 announced that the Government has accepted the recommendations of the Report and that steps would be taken to create a single, unified exchange-traded market for corporate bonds. The measures already taken in respect of implementation of the recommendations of the Patil Committee include:

(a) The Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1956 has been amended to include securitized instruments within the ambit of 'securities'.

(b) The RBI Act has been amended to empower RBI to develop and regulate market for Repos in corporate bonds.

(c) The limit of FII Investment in corporate debt has been increased from US\$ 0.5 billion to US\$ 1.5 billion.

(d) The trade reporting platform for corporate bonds has been operationalised since January 1, 2007.

The trading platforms for corporate bonds at the major exchanges have been operationalised from July 1, 2007.

5) Securities Contracts (Regulation) Amendment Act, 2007: The Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1956 has been amended to include securitization instruments under the definition of 'securities' and provide for disclosure based regulation for issue of the securitized instruments and the procedure thereof. This has been done keeping in view that there is considerable potential in the securities market for the certificates or instruments under securitization transactions. The development of the securitized debt market is critical for meeting the homogenous requirements of the infrastructure sector, particularly housing sector in the country. Replication of the securities markets framework for these instruments would facilitate trading on stock exchanges and in turn help development of the market in terms of depth and liquidity.

6) Permanent Account Number (PAN) As the Sole Identification Number: PAN has been made the sole identification number for all transactions in securities market. This is an investor friendly measure as he does not have to maintain different identification numbers for different kinds of transactions/different segments in financial markets. Further, identification through PAN would help the authorities in enforcement action.

7) Equity Finance for the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs): SMEs in India have traditionally relied on debt financing from banks and non-bank financial institutions. In order to develop the equity market for SMEs, SEBI has decided to create a separate exchange for the SMEs. It has decided that, to begin with there should be a single exchange for the SME sector for around 2-3 years to enable successful development of the market for SMEs.

8) IPO Grading: SEBI has made it compulsory for companies coming out with IPOs of equity shares to get their IPOs graded by at least one credit rating

agency registered with SEBI from May 1, 2007. This measure is intended to provide the investor with an informed and objective opinion expressed by a professional rating agency after analyzing factors like business and financial prospects, management quality and corporate governance practices etc. Till January 2008, 45 IPOs have been graded by credit rating agencies.

- 9) Permitting Indian Mutual Funds to Invest in Overseas Securities:** SEBI has fixed the aggregate ceiling for overseas investments at US \$ 5 billion. Within the overall limit of US \$ 5 billion, mutual funds can make overseas investments subject to a maximum of US \$300 million per mutual fund. Further different regulations that allow individuals and Indian mutual funds to invest in overseas securities by permitting individuals to invest through Indian mutual funds have been converged.
- 10) New Derivative Products:** Mini derivative contract on Index (Sensex and Nifty) having a minimum contract size of Rs. 1 lakh have been introduced. It has been found that globally overall market liquidity and participation generally increases with introduction of mini contracts. Since January 11, 2008 SEBI has also allowed trading on options contracts on indices and stocks with a longer life/tenure of up to five years. These contracts are expected to provide liquidity at the longer end of the market. Since January 15, 2008 SEBI has permitted introduction of volatility index on futures and options contracts. An openly available and quoted measure of market volatility in the form of an index will help market participants.
- 11) Short Selling:** In pursuance to budget announcement, SEBI has issued a circular on December 20, 2007 to permit short selling by institutional investors and securities lending and borrowing to support settlement of short sales.
- 12) Investment Options for Navaratna and Miniratna Public Sector Enterprises:** The Navaratna and Miniratna Public Sector Enterprises have been allowed to invest in public sector mutual funds subject to the condition that they would not invest more than 30 percent of the available surplus funds in equity mutual funds and the Boards of PSEs would decide the guidelines, procedures

and management control systems for such investment in consultation with their administrative Ministries.

13) Investor Protection and Education Fund (IPEF): SEBI has set up the Investor Protection and Education Fund (IPEF) with the purpose of investor education and related activities. SEBI has contributed a sum of Rs. 10 crore toward the initial corpus of the IPEF from the SEBI General Fund. In addition following amounts will also be credited to the IPEF namely;

- (a) Grants and donations given to IPEF by the Central Government, State Governments or any institution approved by SEBI for the purpose of the IPEF;
- (b) Interest or other income received out of the investments made from the IPEF; and
- (c) Such other amount that SEBI may specify in the interests of the investors.

14) Takeover Regulation: Certain amendments were sought in Sept 2002 to the SEBI (Substantial Acquisition of Shares and Takeovers) Regulations, 1997, relating to relaxation for disinvestments of PSUs, additional disclosure requirements, etc. The SEBI also announced an amnesty scheme to enable individuals and companies to disclose irregularities in reporting acquisition of shares.

15) Retail Trading in Government Securities: With a view to encourage wider participation of all classes of investors in government securities, through a nation-wide network screen base trading was launched from January 2003

16) EDIFAR: Electronic Data and Information Filing and Retrieval system was launched by the SEBI to facilitate electronic filing of information by listed companies.

17) Introduction of Rolling Settlement: Extended to all the scrips on all stock exchanges from December 2001. Reducing settlement period from T+5 to T+2 with ultimate aim to bring it at T+1 day in near future.

18) Dematerialization of Scrips: Another material development which proved to be of immense relief to the investors was dematerialization of the scrips. Now 99 percent of the scrips in the market are dematerialized. Almost 100 percent of

the trades are in D-mat form. Inconvenience of physical custody and transfer, medium of intimating change of address and problems of bad delivery, late delivery and the risks of forgery and frauds have virtually disappeared or we can say have been dematerialized. The benefit is relished but not the cost.

POLICY INITIATIVES IN PRIMARY MARKET

The policy initiatives that have been undertaken in the primary market during 2006-07 include:-

1. SEBI has notified the disclosures and other related requirements for companies desirous of issuing Indian depository receipts in India. It has been mandated that:
 - a) The issuer must be listed in its home country;
 - b) It must not have been barred by any regulatory body; and
 - c) It should have a good track record of compliance of securities market regulations.
2. As a condition of continuous listing, listed companies have to maintain a minimum level of public shareholding at 25 per cent of the total shares issued. The exemptions include:-
 - a) Companies which are required to maintain more than 10 per cent, but less than 25 per cent in accordance with the Securities Contracts (Regulation) Rules, 1957; and
 - b) Companies that have two crore or more of listed shares and Rs. 1,000 crore or more of market capitalization.
3. SEBI has specified that shareholding pattern will be indicated by listed companies under three categories, namely, 'shares held by promoter and promoter group'; 'shares held by public' and 'shares held by custodians and against which depository receipts have been issued'.
4. In accordance with the guidelines issued by SEBI, the issuers are required to state on the cover page of the offer document whether they have opted for an IPO (Initial Public Offering) grading from the rating agencies. In case the issuers opt for a grading, they are required to disclose the grades including the unaccepted grades in the prospectus.

5. SEBI has facilitated a quick and cost effective method of raising funds, termed as 'Qualified Institutional Placement' (QIP) from the Indian securities market by way of private placement of securities or convertible bonds with the Qualified Institutional Buyers.
6. SEBI has stipulated that the benefit of 'no lock-in' on the pre-issue shares of an unlisted company making an IPO, currently available to the shares held by Venture Capital Funds (VCFs)/Foreign Venture Capital Investors (FVCIs), shall be limited to:-
 - a) The shares held by VCFs or FVCIs registered with SEBI for a period of at least one year as on the date of filing draft prospectus with SEBI; and
 - b) The shares issued to SEBI registered VCFs/FVCIs upon conversion of convertible instruments during the period of one year prior to the date of filing draft prospectus with SEBI.
7. In order to regulate pre-issue publicity by companies which are planning to make an issue of securities, SEBI has amended the 'Disclosure and Investor Protection Guidelines' to introduce 'Restrictions on Pre-issue Publicity'. The restrictions, inter alia, require an issuer company to ensure that its publicity is consistent with its past practices, does not contain projections/ estimates/ any information extraneous to the offer document filed with SEBI.

POLICY INITIATIVES IN SECONDARY MARKET

Similarly, the policy initiatives that have been undertaken in the secondary market during 2006-07 include:-

1. In continuation of the comprehensive risk management system put in place since May 2005 in T+2 rolling settlement scenario for the cash market, the stock exchanges have been advised to update the applicable Value at Risk (VaR) margin at least 5 times in a day by taking the closing price of the previous day at the start of trading and the prices at 11:00 a.m., 12:30 p.m., 2:00 p.m. and at the end of the trading session. This has been done to align the risk management framework across the cash and derivative markets.

2. In order to strengthen the 'Know Your Client' norms and to have sound audit trail of the transactions in the securities market, 'Permanent Account Number (PAN)' has been made mandatory with effect from January 1, 2007 for operating a beneficiary owner account and for trading in the cash segment.
3. In order to implement the proposal on creation of a unified platform for trading of corporate bonds, SEBI has stipulated that the BSE Limited would set up and maintain the corporate bond reporting platform. The reporting shall be made for all trades in listed debt securities issued by all institutions such as banks, public sector undertakings, municipal corporations, corporate bodies and companies.
4. In line with the Government of India's policy on foreign investments in infrastructure companies in the Indian securities market, the limits for foreign investment in stock exchanges, depositories and clearing corporations, have been specified as follows:-
 - (i) Foreign investment up to 49 per cent will be allowed in these companies with a separate Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) cap of 26 per cent and cap of 23 per cent on Foreign institutional investment (FII);
 - (ii) FDI will be allowed with specific prior approval of Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB);
 - (iii) FII will be allowed only through purchases in the secondary market; and
 - (iv) FII shall not seek and will not get representation on the board of directors.
5. The application process of FII investment has been simplified and new categories of investment (insurance and reinsurance companies, foreign central banks, investment managers, international organizations) have been included under FII.
6. Initial issue expenses and dividend distribution procedure for mutual funds have been rationalised.
7. Mutual funds have been permitted to introduce Gold Exchange Traded Funds.

8. In the Government securities market, the RBI has ceased to participate in primary issues of Central Government securities, in line with the provisions of Fiscal Responsibility and Budget Management Act (FRBM Act).
9. Foreign institutional investors have been allowed to invest in security receipts.

CAPITAL MARKET INNOVATIONS AND BENEFITS DERIVED

There are lots of benefits that flow from the integration and sophistication of capital markets. These are of two kinds, macro-economic and micro-economic.

(I) At the Macro-Economic Level, capital market innovation enlarges the menu of assets available to savers and borrowers. By designing savings vehicles in a more attractive way and extending the reach of financial intermediation, saving is encouraged, and the utility of a given volume of savings to the holders of financial assets is enhanced. Similarly on the borrowing side: the introduction of new borrowing instruments facilitates capital formation and, perhaps even more important, helps improve its quality. If secure and liquid financial assets are readily available, yielding competitive real rates of interest, savings are less likely to be retained by firms for low-productivity investments, or diverted into inflation hedges.

Another macro-economic benefit springs from closer international links among capital markets and financial institutions. The integration of capital markets across borders makes it easier for savings arising in mature economies to be used to finance higher-yielding investment opportunities in economies with higher growth potential. This promotes economic growth in two ways: by improving the efficiency of investment; and by strengthening the discipline on governments and central banks to pursue sound policies.

(II) At the Micro-Economic Level, the development of new financial instruments improves the capacity of financial intermediaries and end-users of financial markets to manage risks. Better risk management, in turn, leads to the improved allocation of resources, in particular capital.

Risk management leads directly to consideration of the role of derivatives. Derivatives are, above all, a means of ‘unbundling’ risks into various elemental components, such as credit risk, interest rates risk, exchange rates risk and so on. This enables the various risk

components to be more clearly identified and priced, and if necessary traded. Derivatives therefore facilitate the adjustment of risk exposures for speculative or hedging purposes. This helps to redistribute risks in the economic system to those most willing, and presumably most able, to bear and manage them.

Derivatives can be tailored to the particular risk management needs of customers. They thereby allow the creation of pay-off characteristics – or hedging possibilities – at a lower cost than would result from the acquisition of underlying assets. This is particularly valuable for those who manage large portfolios such as insurance companies and pension funds, as well as for multinational companies that have streams of payments and receipts subject to the multiple uncertainties of commodity price, exchange rate and interest rate fluctuations.

Another benefit from derivatives markets is the improvement they bring to the mechanism for pricing risks. By enabling composite risks to be broken down into their elemental components, they improve pricing efficiency, and thus the allocation of scarce capital that is needed to cushion risk.

Lastly, derivatives facilitate investment and arbitrage strategies that straddle market segments. They increase asset substitutability, both domestically and internationally. This improves liquidity in individual markets and, it is to be hoped, allows disturbances to be diffused, thus making the overall system more resilient.

In all of these ways, capital market innovations move us towards what are technically known as ‘complete markets’ in this way, they allow market participants to insure themselves against ‘state of the world’ that might adversely affect their business. This is a tremendous advantage. All economic activity involves risk. But if we can allow business and individual to focus on those risks they know and understand, while hedging those risks that are incidental to their main business activity, then efficiency will be improved and long-term investment will be more attractive. To take a simple example: an oil company is more likely to undertake an investment if it can confine its uncertainty to exploration and drilling risk, while buying protection against exchange rate and interest rate risk from financial intermediaries. Financial creativity can improve the risk-return frontier facing individual participants in the real sector of the economy.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the capital market plays a vital role in fostering economic growth of the country, as it augments the quantities of real savings; increases the net capital inflow from abroad; raises the productivity of investments by improving allocation of investible funds; and reduces the cost of capital in the economy. In the liberalized economic environment, the capital market is all set to play a highly critical role in the process of economic development. The Indian capital market has to arrange funds to meet the financial needs of both domestic and foreign resources. What is more critical is that the changed environment is characterized by cutthroat competition. Ability of enterprises to mobilize funds at cheap cost will determine their competitiveness vis-à-vis their rivals.

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